

METROFOOD-RI Pilot Node

Metrology-driven data for safe and sustainable food

FACTSHEET FOR: Researchers; Students; Citizens scientists; Policy makers; Public administration; Business

Pilot Node Profile

METROFOOD-RI is a European research infrastructure supporting food quality, safety, and sustainability through metrology-based data and services.

The node integrates analytical laboratories, reference materials, and data catalogues with the EOSC ecosystem, enabling interoperable, FAIR food data access and cross-disciplinary research.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Federated login to access services {production}
- **Helpdesk**
User support {production}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **METROFOOD-RI Data Catalogues**
(data and service discovery)
- **RM-App**
(reference materials application, instruments)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

1) As a food chemist I want to perform metabolomic analysis of food products to evaluate freshness, flavour, and detect potential contaminants, to study food quality and safety.

Persona: Food chemist analysing product quality and contaminants.

Goal: Perform metabolomic profiling of food samples to assess freshness, flavour and safety using federated data and computing services.

Before: Limited to local datasets and computing power, requiring manual requests and data transfers.

After: Seamless login via EOSC AAI, discovery of food composition datasets in the METROFOOD-RI Catalogue, and large-scale processing on EGI Cloud through the EOSC Discovery Hub - enabling faster, more reproducible, and cross-validated analyses.

2) As a Researcher I want to combine food composition and consumption data with socio-economic indicators across European regions to study dietary quality and support evidence-based food policies.

Persona: Researcher studying dietary inequalities.

Goal: Combine food composition and consumption data from METROFOOD-RI with socio-economic datasets from CESSDA to support evidence-based food policy.

Before: Disparate catalogues with incompatible metadata and time-consuming data alignment.

After: Seamless access via EOSC AAI and federated Helpdesk, harmonised metadata and integrated datasets available through the EOSC Marketplace - enabling efficient cross-disciplinary analysis and policy-relevant food research.

METROFOOD-RI Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- Service Catalogue
- AAI
- Discovery Hub
- Helpdesk
- Monitoring

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- EGI Cloud Compute (computing)
- CESSDA Data Catalogue

Value of the Node piloting activities

The integration of METROFOOD-RI services and datasets with the Core Federating Capabilities delivered by EOSC Beyond introduces new functionalities that enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability across food science and related research domains.

By combining existing METROFOOD-RI resources, such as its Data Catalogue, Reference Materials App, and analytical tools, with EOSC Core services, the pilot enables seamless access to food quality services and nutrition data through a unified interface.

Researchers can now efficiently connect distributed resources, perform large-scale analyses using federated computing environments, and collaborate across institutional and disciplinary domains.

METROFOOD-RI also contributes to defining the technical and procedural frameworks for future food and nutrition infrastructures joining EOSC, providing a model for federating domain-specific catalogues and services within a broader European Open Science ecosystem.

Next steps

The next phase will focus on extending the integration of METROFOOD-RI services with additional EOSC Core components and validating the full workflow across Nodes.

METROFOOD-RI will finalise the deployment of the Service Monitoring, extend metadata harvesting

through OpenAIRE (OAI-PMH), and integrate the Search & Compare App as part of its service portfolio.

Further testing will address interoperability and metadata harmonisation to ensure seamless discovery and reuse of food-related datasets.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

METROFOOD-RI Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/metrofood-ri>

METROFOOD-RI catalogue:

<https://catalogues.staging.metrofood-services.eu>